

Photoelectrochemistry of azure dyes in phospholipid liposome

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The systems consisting of azure (Az) dyes in presence of sonicated aqueous dispersion of phospholipid generate photovoltage when studied in a photoelectrochemical cell. A possible mechanism of photovoltage generation suggests the photoinduced electron transfer from phospholipid to Az dye in liposome. The electrode kinetics of the photoinduced redox reactions in the cell have also been studied to confirm the mechanism of photoinduced electron transfer as well as the interaction between Az dye and phospholipid.

The studies of photoinduced electron transfer or redox reactions in model biomembranes are very interesting and relevant to the understanding of photobiology¹. These model biomembranes are widely used to build biomimetic systems where essential features of green plant photosynthesis are utilized². In these systems, different photosensitive dyes/pigments are incorporated in model membranes. The system may be designed to serve different purposes but the basic process always remains the same, namely, the production of charge carriers and their separation which takes place due to light induced excitation of the photosensitive dyes/pigments at the interfaces. Light induced effects leading to photovoltage generation in bilayer lipid membranes (BLM) and bilayer lipid vesicles (liposome) incorporating dyes/pigments or redox couples have been investigated³⁻¹⁰. We have studied the kinetics of photoinduced electron transfer at the illuminated electrode in a photoelectrochemical cell consisting of phenosafranine and thionine dyes in sonicated aqueous dispersions of egg phosphatidylcholine (PC) and its different fragments, such as lyso-PC, phosphorylcholine and choline^{8,9}; the results help us to confirm the mechanism of photovoltage generation in the cell. In this paper, we report the photoelectrochemical studies of azure (Az) dyes such as Az A, Az B and Az C in sonicated aqueous dispersions of PC, lyso PC, phosphorylcholine and choline including the kinetics of photoinduced electron transfer at the illuminated electrode in support of the mechanism leading to photovoltage generation.

Results and Discussion

A photovoltage is observed on illumination of one compartment of the photoelectrochemical cell consisting of Az dye (1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) and phospholipid liposome (1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) and a platinum electrode, with a dark saturated calomel electrode as a counter electrode in the other

compartment. The illuminated compartment acts as an anode. The photovoltage attains a maximum value within a few minutes. When the illumination is stopped, the photovoltage decays gradually and very nearly reaches the original dark value. This suggests that a reversible photoinduced reaction is initiated in the system for at least 4-5 cycles. The growth and decay of the photovoltage as a function of the time of irradiation of the anode compartment for all the systems consisting of Az dyes (Az A, Az B and Az C) in the presence of PC and its components, except choline chloride are shown in Fig. 1 at 298 K. The system consisting of choline chloride in presence of Az dye does not produce any photovoltage. During the generation of photovoltage, there is no bleaching of the dye solution and photovoltage is generated, even if the solution is not deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen. These observations support the participation of excited singlet Az dye ($^1\text{Az}^+$) in the photovoltage generation since the excited triplet state functions only in deoxygenated solution and rule out the possibility of generating reduced semi-Az dye (AzH^+), the metastable species, which undergoes dismutation to form colourless leuco-Az dye (AzH_2^+ or AzH_2^{2+}). The open-circuit photovoltages (V) of the Az dye-phospholipid liposome systems are mentioned in Table 1.

It is interesting to mention that the photovoltage growth and decay in the dye-phospholipid systems follow the rate equations (1) and (2), respectively in the following forms :

$$V_t = V_0 [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_1)] \quad (1)$$

$$V_t = V_0 [\exp(-t/\tau_{-1})] \quad (2)$$

where V_t is the open-circuit photovoltage at time t , V_0 the steady-state maximum photovoltage and τ is the relaxation time. The relaxation time which is related to the inverse of the rate constant of the respective reactions¹³ plays an im-

Fig. 1. Growth and decay of photovoltage induced by light using platinum electrode and counter dark saturated calomel electrode at 298 K for the Az dye-phospholipid systems in sonicated aqueous dispersion. Figures (a), (b) and (c) correspond to Az A, Az B and Az C, respectively, while the numbers 1 to 3 refer to PC, lyso PC and PCC (Ca salt), respectively.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln V_0/(V_0 - V_t)$ against t for growth (above) and plots of $\ln V_0/V_t$ against t for decay (below) for the Az dye-phospholipid systems in sonicated aqueous dispersion at 298 K. Figures (a), (b) and (c) correspond to Az A, Az B and Az C, respectively, and the numbers 1 to 3 refer to PC, lyso PC and Ca salt of PCC, respectively.

Table 1. Open-circuit photovoltages, relaxation times, rate constants, equilibrium constants (kinetic and spectral) of Az dye-phospholipid systems in aqueous dispersion at 298 K. Concentration of Az dyes, 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ and that of phospholipids in liposomal system, 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³

Dye	Phospholipid	Photovoltage mV	Relaxation time (min)		Rate constant		K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)*	
			Growth τ_1	Decay τ_{-1}	k_1 min ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ dm ³	k_{-1} min ⁻¹	Kinetic k_1/k_{-1}	Spectral ^d
Az A	PC	176	3.62	8.97	1.65×10^3	1.11×10^{-1}	1.49×10^4	8.09×10^3
	Lyso PC	136	5.43	9.73	8.14×10^2	1.03×10^{-1}	7.90×10^3	7.00×10^3
	PCC	90	7.98	11.96	4.17×10^2	8.36×10^{-2}	5.01×10^3	3.02×10^3
Az B	PC	86	8.92	16.55	5.17×10^2	6.04×10^{-2}	8.56×10^3	6.15×10^3
	Lyso PC	50	13.98	19.97	2.14×10^2	5.00×10^{-2}	4.28×10^3	3.03×10^3
	PCC	29	19.98	24.96	1.00×10^2	4.00×10^{-2}	2.50×10^3	2.29×10^3
Az C	PC	275	1.36	5.59	5.56×10^3	1.79×10^{-1}	3.16×10^4	1.20×10^4
	Lyso PC	200	3.06	6.71	1.78×10^3	149×10^{-1}	1.19×10^4	8.55×10^3
	PCC	124	6.97	10.76	5.05×10^2	9.29×10^{-2}	5.44×10^3	4.12×10^3

*Kinetic values referring to excited state interaction should be higher compared to the spectral values referring to ground state interaction.

^dValues taken from Ref.18.

portant role in the kinetics of chemical reactions^{8,9,14-17}. The plots of $\ln V_0/(V_0 - V_t)$ vs time for growth and $\ln V_0/V_t$ vs time for decay are linear in all cases (Fig. 2) and the relaxation times for growth and decay have been calculated from the slopes of these plots, respectively. Eqns. (1) and (2) are based on first order reactions. With a higher concentration of the phospholipid than of the dye, the reactions are expected to be pseudo-first order (light) and first order (dark). Under these conditions, τ_1 is equal to $\{k_1[PL] + k_{-1}\}^{-1}$ in the light reactions, where [PL] is the concentration (mol dm⁻³) of phospholipid and τ_{-1} is equal to $(k_{-1})^{-1}$. Using these relations, the rate constants for the forward (k_1) and

the backward (k_{-1}) reactions have been calculated. All the parameters of electrode kinetics are given in Table 1 including the equilibrium constants of the dye-phospholipid interaction from spectral studies¹⁸ as well as from kinetic studies. The spectral studies also show that the composition of the complex is 1 : 1 dye-phospholipid molecules.

A possible mechanism of photoinduced electron transfer from the phospholipid to the Az dye (Az⁺) leading to the generation of photovoltage in a photoelectrochemical cell is as follows :

The other electrode reactions are

$\text{Hg} + \text{Cl}^- \rightarrow 1/2 \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2 + e^-$ at the sintered glass membrane in light. The sintered glass membrane acts as a double electrode¹⁹, with oxidation at one side (dark) and reduction at the other (light). Among these electrode reactions, only $\text{PL}^{**} + e^- \rightarrow \text{PL}$ is considered here as the cathode reaction in the photoelectrochemical cell.

The overall forward (light) and backward (dark) reaction in the cell under continuous illumination is represented by

According to the Nernst equation²⁰ for a one-electron transfer, the electrode potentials of the anode and the cathode are (activity terms are replaced by concentration terms for dilute solution)

$$E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+} = E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+}^0 - RT/F \ln [\text{Az}^*]/[\text{Az}^+] \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and, } E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}} &= E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}}^0 - RT/F \ln [\text{PL}]/[\text{PL}^{**}] \\ &= E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}}^0 + RT/F \ln [\text{PL}^{**}]/[\text{PL}] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The open-circuit photovoltage (V) of the cell is

$$\begin{aligned} V &= E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}} - E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+} \\ &= E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}}^0 - E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+}^0 + RT/F \ln [\text{Az}^*][\text{PL}^{**}]/[\text{Az}^+][\text{PL}] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Since no photovoltage is generated in the absence of phospholipid, the interaction between the Az dye and the phospholipid is mainly responsible for the generation of photovoltage through the formation of an excited state charge transfer (CT) complex by eqn. (4). The excited state CT is formed by the transfer of an electron from the phospholipid (electron donor) to the excited singlet Az dye (electron acceptor). The generation of electroactive species through excited state CT interaction under continuous illumination causes photovoltage generation in the photoelectrochemical cell. The intermediate complex formation due to CT interaction is assumed to be the slowest step in the photoinduced electron transfer from the phospholipid to the Az dye, as indicated by the equilibrium constant value obtained from the spectral studies¹⁸ as well as from the kinetic studies. Assuming $[\text{Az}^*][\text{PL}^{**}]/[\text{Az}^+][\text{PL}]$ is equal to K , the equilibrium constant of the Az dye-phospholipid complex in the

excited state according to eqn. (4), eqn. (10) becomes

$$V = E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}}^0 - E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+}^0 + 2.303 RT/F \log K \quad (11)$$

Eqn. (11) shows that there should be a linear relation between the photovoltage (V) and the logarithm of the equilibrium constant (K) of the Az dye-phospholipid complex, where $E_{\text{PL}^{**}/\text{PL}}^0$ is considered to be almost the same in all these phospholipids, as they possess a common interacting unit, i.e. phosphorylcholine unit, and $E_{\text{Az}^*/\text{Az}^+}^0$ is expected to differ slightly for the three dyes. The relation between V and $\log K$ is presented in Fig. 3, which is a straight line.

Fig. 3. Plots of photovoltage (V) against $\log K$ of the Az dye-phospholipid systems at 298 K. Figures (a), (b) and (c) correspond to Az A, Az B and Az C, respectively, and the numbers 1 to 3 refer to PC, lyso PC and PCC (Ca salt), respectively.

Thus the relation between the photovoltage generated in a photoelectrochemical cell consisting of Az dyes in phospholipid liposome and the equilibrium constant of the dye-phospholipid interaction in the excited state supports the mechanism of photoinduced electron transfer from the phospholipid to the singlet Az dye leading to the generation of photovoltage in the dye-phospholipid aqueous dispersion system.

From the thermodynamic and spectrophotometric results presented in our earlier report¹⁸, it has been concluded that the electron donating abilities of PC and its components to the Az dyes are in the order : PC > lyso PC > PCC. This is in accordance with the larger alkyl hydrocarbon chain in PC which, in turn, increases the electron density at the electron-

donating centre of the molecule due to inductive effect. On the other hand, the electron-accepting strengths of the Az dyes in this study are in the order : Az C > Az A > Az B, and this is also supported by the spectral studies of Az dyes in surfactant solution²¹. Phospholipids in water form ordered aggregate structures which are very important for interaction with Az dyes. The catalytic role of the aggregation of PC and lyso PC in water, where the liposome provides the necessary surface area for dye absorption, can help in a greater interaction with Az dyes, though the phospholipid donates an electron from the negatively charged oxygen atom of the phosphoryl unit⁸, which is common to PC and its components lyso PC and PCC.

Experimental

All the azure (Az) dyes (Sigma) were recrystallized from ethanol-water. Commercially available PC (L- α -phosphatidylcholine, β -oleoyl, γ -palmitoyl), lyso PC (L- α -lysophosphatidylcholine, oleoyl), phosphorylcholine (PCC) as calcium salt and choline chloride (Sigma) were used without further purification. Aqueous solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The experimental techniques for liposome preparation by sonication of phospholipid dispersion in water have been described earlier¹².

The photoelectrochemical cell consisted of an H-shaped cell with all standard joint stoppers; the details of the experimental set-up for the measurement of photovoltage were schematically presented earlier¹⁰. In this cell, the illuminated and the dark chambers (2 cm apart) were separated by a sintered glass membrane (G-4). Both the chambers were of the same dimension (dia. 2 cm; height, 8 cm). A platinum foil electrode was placed in the illuminated chamber and a counter saturated calomel electrode was placed in the dark chamber. The light source was a 300 W tungsten projector lamp with an intensity of 30 mW cm⁻². The photovoltage was measured by connecting the electrodes to a Keithley 642 electrometer.

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